

Harnessing the Power of Curiosity: A Pathway to Success and Fulfillment

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Preface—OnePercent was founded on the belief that education should nurture curiosity, not suppress it. This paper presents the core research that shaped our approach to building curiosity-driven learning systems. The findings and framework discussed here serve as the foundation for OnePercent's mission to make learning more purposeful, creative, and fulfilling for every student.

Abstract—In the modern educational landscape, learning extends beyond the transfer of knowledge and includes the development of essential skills such as creativity, problem-solving, critical thinking, communication, and teamwork. However, there is growing dissatisfaction with conventional education systems, particularly in how students are taught facts and methodologies without understanding their real-world relevance. Many students pursuing higher studies lack awareness of the significance of what they learn or are driven by external motivations, which often leads to stress and an unfulfilling academic experience. This paper introduces an approach that leverages humanity's innate curiosity to help students find purpose in their learning journey. The proposed methodology aims to enhance student-teacher engagement, promote creativity and critical thinking, and encourage students to research and explore diverse opportunities to make informed and unbiased career decisions. Such purposeful and self-driven choices are more likely to lead to a happier, more successful, and meaningful life.

Keywords—curiosity, education, purpose, learning, interest, skill development, career choice, creativity, critical thinking, problem-solving, student engagement, curriculum enhancement, success, happiness

I. INTRODUCTION

Education and skill development, especially in the modern era, are of utmost importance to succeed in life; skills like creativity, problem-solving and teamwork are vital components that assist knowledge and experience in the corporate world [1][2]. Education also positively impacts one's personal development and happiness, both in the short term and the long term. It can help people network, find purpose and meaning in life and achieve a sense of community that humans crave so much [3].

The science and the statistics are clear that education, especially a college education leads to better-paying jobs and eventually a better life [4][5][6]. However, dropouts are ubiquitous and those who drop out are particularly more struggling psychologically [7]. Even the ones who make it to the workforce with some sort of education or skills, most of them end up hating their careers [8]. Although many factors like less pay, lack of work-life balance, and bad working environment, etc. lead to this resentment, the primary pattern comes down to a lack of purpose and fulfilment in one's professional life. Sports persons are examples of those who work most of the time and still enjoy

it, all because they love what they do and find purpose and meaning in it.

The importance of one's love for the work they do is unequivocal[9] but the challenge is to enable people to find that purpose. The real challenge of education is not the lack of ultimate knowledge but the inability to instil purpose and interest. This paper presents a unique approach to instilling interest, especially in those fields like science and engineering which are mainly sought after for the money and not for one's love for the field.

Technology has enabled information to be at everybody's fingertips and the vast majority of people don't make use of it [10]. This is a clear indicator that it's not the technology that needs more focus and improvement but the soft science of how to encourage and motivate people to make use of it.

Additionally, the problem with traditional education is that most institutes focus on memorizing facts and methods, instead of enabling critical thinking and improving a student's problem-solving capabilities. There's no doubt that knowledge is of utmost importance but it's of no use if students are not seeing the use of it. Students wonder why they need to study certain subjects and this makes them feel disconnected which leads to resentment and eventually, loss of interest in their education.

This study aims to change this and showcase the importance of a pupil's curiosity and the significance of harnessing its power. The subject of mathematics is used as an example as it's not just a subject, but a skill that's used in all areas of life. Despite its significance, it's the most resented one [11]. Although many have tried to address this issue [12][13], there hasn't been much of a difference in students' perceptions. By understanding students' feelings about mathematics, how they feel about its importance and how their interests and experiences shape them, curiosity's impact on one's education as well as career choice can be understood. It presents a unique approach to making use of curiosity, the same inherent quality of humanity that's enabled exploration, given rise to unthinkable innovations and continues to drive humanity forward [14]. It discusses the role of curiosity in education and how it helps students do better in school, make good career choices, improve the odds of success, more importantly, to live a happy and fulfilling life.

In the next sections, the implications of the research are shared which includes how curiosity can make education better and ways to help students stay curious. Additionally, curiosity's power to enable students to choose careers that fit them well is also discussed. By paying more attention to curiosity, education can be more exciting and helpful and prepare students not just for exams but for a successful and fulfilling life ahead.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Before diving into the research, it's important to discuss the strides made so far and the suggested methodologies to make education more appealing and fulfilling.

Corey Seemiller, Meghan Grace, Paula Dal Bo Campagnolo, Isa Mara Da Rosa Alves and Gustavo Severo De Borba gave some valuable insights into how students love learning about topics they are interested in [15]. Additionally, Kahu, Ella & Nelson, Karen & Picton and Catherine in their research, concluded that students tend to be more interested in topics that are relevant to their future careers [16]. These conclusions apply to any field be it science and engineering or arts and humanities. However, not a lot of students fall into this category. The conclusion of these research papers may be flawless but it addresses such a small portion of the crowd without a solid solution to get more people interested in subjects to positively impact society.

So, how to get students interested in a subject in the first place? Furthermore, it should also be something that's going to positively affect their lives and have demand in this ever-changing landscape of the workforce. Petr and Tomáš, in their research, suggest ways to develop more interest in STEM (Science Technology Engineering Mathematics) related subjects [17]. One of the primary ways to do it includes showing students how prevalent science is in everyday life. Although this takes a step further than just teaching concepts and making students solve problems using those concepts, it fails to engage students in critical thinking. The core of innovation has been exploring innovative approaches and solving problems. This can only be done by people who "think outside the box" and solve problems and not get better at existing methodologies. This is what the current system is depriving young minds of, the power to think differently. Therefore, we need a method or a system that showcases the widespread use of concepts taught in schools and colleges as well as engages students in critical thinking to enable them to be change-bringers.

Furthermore, people's lives are filled with distractions, especially in the age of the internet. Therefore, whatever method is employed to develop an interest in students, it has to be strong enough to overcome the distractions in their lives. [18] Shelly J and Schmidt talk about various ways to overcome distractions such as motivation, discipline, etc. but motivation is short-lived and discipline is something hard to come by for most people. However, one of the solutions includes an effective and engaging learning environment where students feel a sense of purpose. A purpose that can keep one occupied and the stronger the calling of the purpose, the less one would be affected by distractions.

This further begs the question, how to enable and help students to find a purpose? To answer this, we need to look at what factors contribute to their career choices currently. Petr, Tomáš, and Renáta in their research, shed light on the different factors that contribute to shaping one's career choices, with one's surroundings topping the list [19]. For example, parents and relatives who are in a particular field are likely to encourage others to pursue the career if they're happy and pursue another if they are not satisfied, often that they think they should have chosen. This is not just bad advice but limits students' perspectives and also stops them

from looking at other career opportunities with an open mind.

Additionally, Cooper N sheds light on the effects of media on a pupil's career, especially biases that can be harmful in the long run [20]. It's no coincidence that the most sought-after careers are the ones that are glorified by the media worldwide.

Therefore it's of utmost importance to not just recognize that students perform better in subjects they're interested in, but also to help them develop this purpose on their own with an open mind giving it enough thought and research without anybody's views affecting their choices in any way. This paper presents a way to instil curiosity in students at the school/college level and let them build upon it which would not only increase their chances of succeeding but enable them to live a happy and fulfilled life.

III. METHODOLOGY

A. Research Design

For this study, a quantitative research design was employed to investigate the relationship between curiosity, learning, and career choices among engineering students. The choice of the approach was motivated by the need to quantitatively measure curiosity levels, subject preferences, and perceptions of its importance.

B. Data Collection

Data was collected through a structured survey administered to a diverse sample of men and women in both undergraduate and postgraduate engineering courses. The sample included students from various engineering departments to ensure a diverse set of opinions. In-person surveys were conducted to ensure that the data collected was genuine and authentic. Participation was voluntary and ensured anonymity to encourage candid responses. Furthermore, ethical considerations were upheld, and participants were informed of the purpose of the study.

C. Survey Instrument

The survey questionnaire comprised 4 distinct sections which are as follows

1) Exploring Mathematical Preferences and Awareness of its Significance

This section of the survey aimed to gain insights into participants' perceptions of the subject of mathematics and their awareness of its real-world applications. The primary objectives were to assess participants' liking for mathematics and uncover potential connections between awareness of real-world applications and subject likability shedding light on the relationships between knowledge, preferences, and the awareness of the significance of mathematics in the real world.

Question 1: Subject Likeability

To begin, participants were asked to rate their level of liking for the subject of mathematics. Using a scale ranging from 1 which stood for "Strongly

Dislike" to 10 which equalled "Strongly Like", respondents were invited to express their sentiments toward mathematics.

Question 2: Preferred Concept and Associated Real-Life Applications

Continuing the survey, participants were prompted to identify a specific mathematical concept that they found engaging or appealing. Alongside this concept, respondents were asked to provide examples of real-life scenarios or applications where this mathematical concept is relevant and utilized.

Question 3: Non-Preferred Concept and Associated Real-Life Applications

Similarly, participants were further asked to specify a mathematical concept that they found less appealing. Alongside this concept, respondents were invited to elucidate instances from everyday life where this less-liked mathematical concept is applicable or holds real-world implications.

2) Perception of Mathematics in Everyday Life

In this section, participants were prompted to reflect on their perception of the role of mathematics in everyday objects and technologies, to uncover potential shifts in their perceptions over time. The primary objectives were to gauge participants' current perceptions of mathematics' significance and to explore any variations between their present views and those held when they were in Grade 10. The choice of Grade 10 holds significance as it marks a pivotal moment when students contemplate their academic and career trajectories. The survey aimed to elucidate whether participants tended to underestimate or overestimate the importance of mathematics in the real world, especially in comparison to their perceptions during the critical Grade 10 decision-making phase.

Question 1: Current Perception of the Role of Mathematics in Everyday Life

Participants were asked to rate the extent to which they believe mathematics plays a role in everyday objects and technologies. Using a scale from 1 to 10, where 1 signifies "Negligible Role" and 10 signifies "Significant Role," respondents were invited to assess the degree of mathematics' impact on everyday items like mobile phones, the internet, food and water supply, etc.

Question 2: Perception of the Role of Mathematics in Everyday Life when Students' were in Grade 10

Participants were then asked to consider the same question but in the context of their perceptions during Grade 10. This phase aimed to gather insights into how participants' views about the role of mathematics may have evolved since then.

3) Media and the Surroundings' Impact on Career Aspirations and Shaping Perceptions

This section of the survey delves into the role of media, such as movies and TV shows, plays in influencing individuals' career aspirations and shaping their perceptions about various fields. The primary objectives are to explore participants' childhood aspirations, assess the impact of media in moulding these dreams, and examine how exposure to content promoting entrepreneurship, and medicine, innovation, and engineering might have affected their career inclinations. The survey aims to shed light on the potential positive influence that well-crafted content can have on guiding young minds towards diverse and impactful career paths.

Question 1: Childhood Aspirations

Participants were asked to reflect on their childhood aspirations and share their early dreams and career ambitions.

Question 2: Media's Role in Shaping These Beliefs

Participants were prompted to consider the role that media, such as movies, TV shows, and other forms of entertainment, played in shaping their aspirations during their formative years. This phase aims to evaluate how much media and one's surroundings influence one's career perceptions.

Question 3: Influential Content and Shifting Aspirations

Participants were presented with examples of media content that highlighted entrepreneurship ("Shark Tank"), medicine ("Grey's Anatomy"), innovation/engineering ("The Social Network"), etc. Respondents were then asked to contemplate whether exposure to such content might have influenced them to lean towards careers in these fields instead of their initial aspirations.

4) Exploring the Dynamics of Subject Disliking and Perceived Difficulty

This section of the survey is designed to uncover the relationship between students' attitudes towards subjects and their perceived level of difficulty. The primary focus was to investigate whether students tend to dislike a subject because they find it challenging or if their perception of difficulty arises due to their initial aversion, leading to reduced effort and time investment. Understanding this dynamic is crucial in devising effective strategies to promote vital subjects such as mathematics and science among students as well as determining the complexity of the subjects.

Question 1: Subject Disliking and Perceived Difficulty

Participants were asked to reflect upon how they felt about a subject and their perceived level of difficulty. They were given two situations to consider:

Option 1: Subject Disliking due to Difficulty: Participants were asked if they tend to dislike a

subject primarily because they find it hard to grasp. This scenario aims to determine if perceived difficulty contributes to students' subject aversion.

Option 2: Perceived Difficulty due to Disliking: Conversely, respondents were prompted to consider if they perceive a subject as challenging mainly because they already dislike it. This scenario seeks to explore the reverse cause-and-effect relationship, where initial disinterest influences the perception of subject difficulty as one would end up investing less time and effort due to the aversion.

D. Data Analysis and Interpretation

1) Exploring Mathematical Preferences and Awareness of its Significance

Among the participants, a mere 35.5% were able to name real-life applications for both liked and disliked concepts. This finding highlights a potential gap in the awareness of the practical implications of mathematical knowledge.

27% of participants were able to identify real-life applications solely for concepts they liked, suggesting one of two things, either that they researched about the concepts they like or they like the concept because they know the significance of it.

Conversely, 2% of participants were only able to associate real-life applications with concepts they disliked.

Alarming, the remaining percentage of participants were unable to name any real-life applications for either liked or disliked concepts, underlining the need for enhanced emphasis on connecting education to tangible real-world scenarios.

Fig. 1. Awareness of real-world applications and likeness

Further analysis focused on the relationship between participants' likeness ratings towards mathematics and their ability to identify real-life applications for both liked and disliked concepts.

Among participants who rated their likeness towards math as more than 9 out of 10, a notable

34.48% could successfully name real-life applications for both liked and disliked concepts.

For those who rated above 8, the percentage dropped slightly to 32.43%, suggesting a positive yet diminishing trend in real-life application recognition.

Similarly, participants who rated their likeness above 7 demonstrated a recognition rate of 28.22%, further emphasizing the correlation between high likeness and practical application awareness.

As likeness ratings decreased, the ability to identify real-life applications also declined. Notably, the recognition rate stood at 25% for those who rated 5 and below and further dropped to 22.22% for participants with ratings of 3 and below.

Fig. 2. Correlation between awareness of real-world applications and likeness

In addition to these findings, it is important to note that the survey was conducted among students in Bangalore, at the epicenter of innovation and information technology in India. The data suggests that even among the brightest scientific and engineering minds, the lack of awareness regarding the real-life applications of mathematical concepts is alarming. This observation implies that the situation is much more dire in institutions where the talent and the quality of education are lower.

The correlation between one's likeness of a subject and knowing its importance is clear but the question is to find out which is the "cause" and which is the "effect". Does one research a subject due to the love for the subject or does one realize a subject's importance and then end up liking it as they spend more time on it?

2) Perception of Mathematics in Everyday Life

In this section, we delve into the analysis of participants' perceptions regarding the role of mathematics in everyday life and how these

perceptions have evolved. The survey aimed to shed light on potential shifts in awareness and highlight the influence of pivotal decision-making periods, such as during Grade 10, on students' perceptions of mathematics.

Our analysis reveals a significant revelation regarding the participants' perception of mathematics' importance. On average, participants underestimated the significance of mathematics by 28% during their Grade 10, as compared to their current perception while studying engineering.

Fig. 3. Change in perception regarding the significance of mathematics

This observation underscores a marked shift in participants' awareness and appreciation of mathematics' practical relevance. Despite choosing to pursue engineering (where mathematics is the core concept), participants still acknowledged having considerably underestimated mathematics' importance during their formative years.

This analysis carries broader implications. Despite opting for engineering studies, the lack of awareness of the importance of the applications of the subject would lead to less time being spent studying the subject. This has obvious consequences such as missed potential and increasing resentment towards mathematics and the education system as a whole.

Furthermore, extrapolating this finding to students who did not pursue mathematics-intensive careers may lead to the inference that their underestimation of mathematics' importance could be even more pronounced. The data underscores the critical role of educational institutions in illuminating the practical implications of mathematics, not only for those choosing mathematics-intensive fields but for all students to allow them to make informed decisions.

In conclusion, this section sheds light on the need for educational institutions to bridge the gap

between students' perceptions and the actual significance of mathematics as well as all subjects in everyday life. By imparting a more comprehensive understanding of practical applications, educational institutions can empower students to make informed career choices, fostering a more well-rounded and insightful perspective on the subject's role in various domains and increasing productivity.

3) Media Influence on Aspirations and Career Perceptions

In this section, we delve into the analysis of participants' childhood aspirations, the role of media in shaping their dreams, and the potential impact of specific content on their career inclinations. The survey aimed to illuminate the significance of the media's role in influencing students' aspirations and shaping their future trajectories.

The analysis revealed intriguing insights regarding participants' childhood aspirations. Only a modest 28% of students mentioned fields such as science, research, engineering, and similar intellectually stimulating disciplines. This observation suggests that a substantial portion of participants, the ones that did end up taking engineering/science/research did not initially consider these careers.

Fig. 4. Category of participants' initial aspirations

Further examination focused on the role of media, including movies, TV shows, and sports, in influencing participants' aspirations. The data indicates a strikingly impactful relationship, as an average of 73% of respondents acknowledged that media played a significant role in shaping their dreams. This highlights the powerful role media plays in unconsciously influencing individuals' perceptions of desirable careers.

Additionally, the survey extended its exploration by questioning participants about the potential

influence of specific content on their career decisions. Content such as "Grey's Anatomy" (medicine-focused TV show), "Shark Tank" (entrepreneurship-focused reality show), and "The Social Network" (innovation and computer science-focused movie) was considered. Notably, a substantial 63% of participants responded affirmatively, stating that exposure to such content as children would have likely shaped their inclination towards engineering-related fields.

Fig. 5. If media can influence students to take up science/engineering

These findings collectively underscore the profound influence of media on shaping students' career aspirations and perceptions. Media's role extends far beyond entertainment; it serves as a silent architect of future dreams. The fact that a substantial portion of participants believed that specific content could have guided their career choices highlights the potential to harness media as a tool for educational empowerment.

In conclusion, the power of media in shaping students' dreams cannot be underestimated. The data emphasises the need for content creation that aligns with educational goals, allowing media play a proactive role in nurturing future generations of scientists, engineers, and innovators, those who collectively drive humanity forward.

4) Unraveling the Disliking-Difficulty Dynamic

In this section, we delve into the analysis of participants' responses to a pivotal question: whether they tend to dislike a subject because they find it difficult or if they perceive a subject as challenging due to their existing aversion, leading to reduced effort and engagement. The survey aimed to uncover the cause-and-effect relationship

between subject disliking and perceived difficulty, with implications for educational strategies.

Participants were posed with two distinct options:

Option 1: Disliking a subject because they found it hard.

Option 2: Finding a subject hard as they disliked it and subsequently investing less time and effort into it.

A notable 68% of participants selected Option 2, implying that a subject's perceived difficulty is more likely a consequence of pre-existing aversion. This finding challenges the conventional assumption that the complexity of a subject inherently leads to one's resentment. Instead, it suggests that the root cause of a subject becoming difficult often lies in students' initial lack of interest or engagement.

Fig. 6. Difficulty-Dislike relationship

This observation carries profound implications for educational strategies. By identifying the cause-and-effect relationship between subject disliking and perceived difficulty, we arrive at an essential realization: fostering a love for subjects can be a powerful catalyst for improved performance. Rather than simplifying the complexity of subjects like mathematics and science, the emphasis should be on igniting curiosity and appreciation. Encouraging students to engage more deeply with these subjects can lead to a positive cascade effect: as interest grows, perceived difficulty diminishes, leading to increased dedication and improved performance.

In the subsequent sections, a holistic synthesis of the findings is presented, culminating in a set of recommendations that underscore the crucial role of curiosity in shaping educational paradigms for the better.

IV. IMPLICATION

Section 3's revelations emphasize that media, both knowingly and unknowingly, contributes to shaping dreams. It's evident since many aspirations align with those glorified by the media—actors, sportspersons, doctors, and high-ranking government positions. This pattern suggests that individuals might remain unaware of the diverse opportunities available beyond these highlighted roles, which might have been better and more fulfilling.

While some might argue that information is easily accessible online, this perspective falls short of recognizing the intricacies of human behaviour. The soft science behind why individuals fail to explore beyond the familiar is paramount. Our research acknowledges the complexity lying beyond blunt solutions like "Look it up on the internet". The examination of these behavioural nuances provides a comprehensive understanding of why individuals might not seize the potential at their fingertips.

With strong empirical support from Section 2, we acknowledge that even students within the engineering realm underestimate the significance of subjects critical to their careers. This misalignment between perception and reality suggests that informational gaps persist, even among those being immersed in related fields and are only worse for those not in the field.

Expanding upon Section 2's conclusions, Section 1 further highlights that a profound liking for a subject has a direct correlation with the awareness of its real-life applications. Individuals inclined towards certain concepts display a heightened understanding of their practical implications. Notably, data accentuates that real-life application knowledge is confined to preferred concepts. This interplay between liking and awareness highlights the importance of nurturing interest and understanding in tandem.

Section 4's insights into performance challenges fortify the premises laid out in Section 1. The conclusion that disliking a subject correlates with poorer performance reinforces the notion that awareness of a subject's importance drives research, cultivates interest, and subsequently enhances performance. This alignment between liking, awareness, and performance strengthens the case for an integrated approach to education where one is made aware of each subject's significance not by stating it but by instilling curiosity about its applications

V. PROPOSED SOLUTION

Amidst the challenges posed by media's influence and limited awareness of diverse opportunities, there exists a transformative solution. By infusing education with a curiosity-driven approach, we can empower students to become active seekers of knowledge, critical thinkers, and creators of their educational journey. This proposed solution advocates for a shift from traditional instruction to questioning-based learning, a pedagogical approach that stimulates curiosity, fosters independent thinking and paves the way for a holistic understanding of subjects and their applications.

Below are some examples of how it can be achieved in schools and accordingly, similar examples can be employed in universities.

- **Physics: Embracing Relativity's Mysteries**
Rather than presenting the Theory of Relativity as a set of equations, educators can ignite curiosity by asking, "Why do the astronauts aboard the International Space Station age slower than the people on Earth?". This enables students to think critically and realize the practical implications of Einstein's theory of relativity once it's presented. It enables them to delve into the intricacies of space-time, fostering a deeper connection between theoretical physics and the real world.
- **Chemistry: The Power of the Sun**
Educators can arouse curiosity by posing questions like "How does the sun produce energy?". This query beckons students to unravel the science of fusion and realize its significance to not just humans but life as we know it. Especially in the current state of the climate of the planet, it's of utmost importance to have deeply curious and motivated scientists and engineers to collectively come up with solutions in the realm of nuclear physics and nuclear chemistry to slow down the degrading state of the planet, especially due to the energy industry.
- **Biology: The battles of the past**
Instead of putting forward Darwin's theory of evolution, educators can instil curiosity by asking, "How did humans come to be the smartest living beings on the planet?". This question sparks the exploration of evolution and the concept of "survival of the fittest" and encourages students to delve deep into the subject, connect the missing dots, and increase the likelihood of mastering biology which is so crucial in the age of globally connected communities spreading diseases exacerbated by poor diets and weak immune systems.
- **Computer Science: Modelling Human Brain**
Instead of putting forward complex computer algorithms, educators can pose questions like "How to make computers think like humans?". This sparks an investigation into artificial neural networks that emulate the neurons of the human brain. By igniting curiosity, we inspire students to dive into the world of artificial intelligence and machine learning, fostering a generation of engineers proficient in harnessing technology's transformative power as well as loving the process.
- **Economics: How Money Works**
Instead of focusing on the rules of Demand and Supply, students can be posed with questions like "Why do people buy Gold during a recession?". This is not only thought-provoking but Economics is something that everybody, irrespective of the career they choose to pursue ought to think and know about, especially in the times when financial literacy is given so less importance in schools.

- **History: Learning through Experience**

Instead of boring students with dates of important events, educators can backtrack by asking questions like “How did Germany and Japan become so prosperous even after the destruction of World War 2?”. This instils curiosity within, similar to a movie’s storytelling. Furthermore, studying history is beneficial to every field from politicians trying to avoid mistakes committed in the past to economics devising plans, therefore, exposing these opportunities to the students blinded by the dates and results of the past wars.

- **Geography: Mapping the Globe**

Educators can make even subjects like Geography interesting by stating their importance and asking thought-provoking questions like “How do mountains form?”. This might be uninteresting to some yet amusing to others, which is what educators ought to achieve, spark a light within and let the students turn it into a fire if it’s of interest to them.

- **Law: The Rules of Governing**

Students can be taught this seemingly theoretical subject by employing the same method and asking questions like “How and why did lawmakers settle on different severity of punishments for different crimes?”. This enables students to think about concepts that they never would’ve thought about and get a brief idea about the work that goes into something that’s taken for granted. It produces more action-takers and change-bringers in law as well as politics instead of complainers and protestors.

Posing thought-provoking questions and including them as a prerequisite while introducing new concepts, not only has a lasting impact on the student’s never-ending journey of self-improvement, but it also leads to a happy and fulfilling life by enabling students to make informed decisions instead of relying on an outside source.

It nullifies the dependence on media for shaping one’s career as the significance is learnt in schools. It also makes pupils aware of the significance of every subject and the concepts learnt in the subjects. Subsequently, this leads to career choices dictated by the love for the subject, which in turn, puts students in a better position to grasp complex topics, take on real-life challenges and contribute to the ever-growing knowledge of the human race.

VI. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

To assess the effectiveness of the proposed solution, a survey was conducted among computer science students. While the examples provided were drawn from diverse fields outside of computer science, participants were asked

to consider how the implementation of the curiosity-based teaching method would have influenced their career choices. The survey aimed to gauge whether the newfound approach to learning would have steered their aspirations towards alternate career paths.

The survey results yielded astounding insights, notably, 85% of the surveyed individuals expressed a strong inclination towards choosing different career paths if they had been exposed to the proposed teaching methods and a further 8% said that they may have ended up in different careers. This affirmative response suggests that the approach of sparking curiosity, posing questions, and encouraging independent thinking resonates with students across disciplines. The openness of these participants to reevaluate their career preferences highlights the potential impact of fostering curiosity and critical thinking in education.

These findings provide preliminary evidence of the viability of the proposed solution. The positive response from computer science students, despite the examples being from fields other than their own, underscores the universal nature of curiosity-driven learning and not just in STEM-related subjects. While the study focused on a specific group of students, the outcomes hint at the broader implications for education across various domains. However, further research involving a larger and more diverse sample size, as well as longitudinal studies, would be instrumental in solidifying the effectiveness and long-term impact of this innovative teaching approach.

VII. CONCLUSION

Despite some challenges, educators embracing a curiosity-driven approach hold the potential to revolutionize learning. Recognizing the limitations of requiring educators to grasp the subject significance and stay current in industries, along with the potential for longer classes, this approach’s cumulative benefits far outweigh its drawbacks.

This research underscores the transformative power of curiosity in education. It establishes that students genuinely curious about subjects not only engage more deeply but also achieve comprehensive understanding. Across subjects like mathematics, science, literature, and arts, etc, curiosity consistently correlates with better academic performance.

The influence of media and one’s surroundings on aspirations emerges as a strong theme. Although controlling media to influence students will be a controversial and highly politicized issue, promoting an even, curiosity-driven teaching model empowers students to ask questions, explore subjects, and uncover passions at a young age in educational institutes instead of relying on other factors.

By nurturing curiosity, educators and institutions hold the key to unleashing potential and guiding students towards unexplored horizons. This methodology’s adoption can reshape education, fostering thinkers, innovators, and societal contributors. As we navigate constant change, curiosity endures as a force driving innovation, excellence, and evolution.

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